

Effects of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative Strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among Secondary School Students in Benue State

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effects of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State. Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non-equivalent research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Population of the study comprise of all government junior secondary school class three (JSSIII), 2022/2023 academic session students with special needs in Benue state. A sample size of 46 (28 Male and 18 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. Instrument used for the study is Interest in Geometry Scale (IGS) with reliability index of 0.76 obtained using Cronbach Alpha. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings in Geometry of students with special needs when taught using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those taught using coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy. In conclusion, Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State. The study recommended among others, that guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy should be encouraged in special secondary schools for students with special needs.

Keywords: Guided-inquiry instructional strategy, coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy, interest, concept geometry, special needs.

Introduction

Geometry is a branch of Mathematics concerned with properties of space such as distance, shape, size and relative position of figures. Mathematics can be defined as the science of structure, order and relationship that has evolved from counting, measuring and describing the shapes of objects. Geometry in its simplest form is the mathematical study of shapes and space. According to Matalone (2021) geometry deals with flat, two-dimensional shapes with depth, such as cubes and spheres, which are created using points, lines, line segments, rays and planes. The relevance of Mathematics concepts such as Geometry in the development of science and technology is crucial because it helps us understand and describe the fundamental properties of the world. Jones (2016) opined that Geometry enables us to solve real-world problems, design structure, and advance various fields: science, engineering and arts.

In Nigeria, Mathematics has been made a compulsory subject from primary to secondary school and also a requirement for admission into the university in science and social science courses. Mathematics is essential in our everyday life endeavors, for understanding and engaging with our world. It enables the development of pupils' natural ability to think logically, solve puzzles and apply these skills to real-life problems. Shimizu and Vithal (2023) posits that Mathematics specifications provides students with access to important mathematical ideas to develop mathematical knowledge and problem-solving skills.

People with special needs are people in need of special help or care because they have a physical disability or a variety of conditions such as an impairment. They are the physically challenged: crippled, blind, deaf, including, the mentally retarded. Not all children are born under normal circumstances; some are born with different conditions and special needs (Sabaruddin, Mansor, Rusmar & Husna, 2019). Those kinds of students will require special treatment in all aspects compared to other children who do not have such issues. Notwithstanding the alarming birth rate of children with special needs, the special

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education centers still record low intake of students with special needs as a result of their parents and guardians neglecting their need for educational development. Ilona (201) found that the birth rate of children with special needs has continued to increase worldwide. Onaolapo and Onaolapo (2017) stated that most of children with special needs face challenges or difficulty in performance especially autistic children. According to Aligba and Nyihemba (2022) it has been observed that a considerable population of school pupils is seen as having either special educational needs (SEN) or learning difficulties as well as disabilities (LDD). Some of these students in special educational schools also have learning difficulties linked to social deprivation, which could make them loss interest in learning Geometry. Learning difficulties experienced by some of these pupils could cause them to lose interest in class activities and at times withdraw from interacting with others both within and outside the class while some may drop out of school. The difficulties faced by pupils with special needs in learning Mathematics concepts could make them lose interest in learning or skip Mathematics classes (Sabaruddin, 2020).

Guided-inquiry strategy provides the opportunity for students to interact by asking questions, seek solutions, analysing and applying their knowledge to solving daily life problems. Guided inquiry instruction strategy (GISS) is an approach whereby the teacher leads his/her students with well formulated questions that are designed to bring students face to face with knowledge they are seeking, so that they can in effect find out such knowledge. According to Eche, Eriba and Gyuse (2021) guided inquiry is a student-centered instruction strategy whereby there is active participation of students in the learning process, it uses classrooms discussions, problem solving, role plays and collaborative learning. Guided-inquiry strategy could ensure that students are given the opportunity to find out things themselves about events and scientific ideas through asking questions, investigation, observation, and construction of reasonable explanation, sharing information and experience (Audu, Ajayi, & Angura, 2017). Guided-inquiry strategy, as an instructional strategy in teaching Geometry could embraces students' deep understanding of the concept.

Coop-Coop Cooperative Learning was developed by Kagan (1989) in (Achor, Jack & Daiko, 2022). In this learning instruction, the teacher guides the process of learning at each phase. The teacher introduces the topic, and breaks it into sub-topics, and groups the students in small groups of 4-6 membered teams. According to Achor, Jack and Daiko, (2022) the teams discuss the instructor's defined topics and select one in which they have an interest, and each team segments its topics into micro-topics for each team member, the team topic must be fully covered. Coop-Coop Cooperate learning is a collaboration and co-operative learning of students in teams. It could be used as one of the cooperative strategies of learning that allows students to work together in small groups to advance their understanding and provide them with the opportunity to share the understanding with their peers. Birt (2023) opined that students can learn behavioural techniques like interpersonal skills, social interaction and collaborative skills that teach them how to work with others. Co-operative learning takes place through the interactions students have with their peers, through male and female interaction with their peers and also through the interactions the students have with their teachers in the learning process.

Interest in learning Mathematics is the willingness to learn mathematical concepts, it's the feeling of curiosity towards learning concepts in Mathematics and applying them in solving life problems. Interest is a vital aspect of the teaching and learning process, because the learners' interest is an essential factor in incubating the right knowledge, skills, values, and morals that the curriculum seeks to attain (Bileya & Achor, 2021). According to Herpratiwi and Tohir (2022) interest in learning accompanies the desire or ability to deliberate attention and liveliness that eventually give birth to a sense of fun in the form of a change of behavior or attitude of knowledge and skills. It could sustain concentration, purpose and commitment of students to learning. The special needs educator has the responsibility to make Mathematics class, comfortable, suitable and interesting for the pupils with special needs by having the ability to practice inclusivity and handle each pupils' special need. The special needs educator could use learning strategies that are learner –centered in boosting the interest of the pupils with special needs, enabling the students participate actively in the class by interaction through co-operation with their peers and answering questions of inquiry accordingly. Interest is an important variable in learning because when one becomes interested in an activity, he or she is likely to become more deeply involved in that activity (Achor, Jack & Daiko, 2022).

Interest affects all the learning domains of the student; the affective, the psychomotor and the cognitive domain of learning. Once a student develops the feeling of curiosity and willingness to learn Mathematics, this could affect his affective domain. This leads to taking actions, and acquiring necessary skills (psychomotor) in learning the concepts and with constant practice he is able to solve mathematical problems, by this, the student's understanding begins to widen and deepen towards cognitively applying mathematical concepts in various problem-solving aspects. Once the students are motivated and stimulated to learn, they will continue to learn as long as the teacher has the capacity to sustain the learners' interest on that object of learning (Herpratiwi & Tohir, 2022).

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From previous studies, guided-inquiry strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies has shown effectiveness in Mathematics concepts learning process. Ijeh (2023) study showed that there is a significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught mathematics with inquiry-based instructional strategy (experimental) group and their counterparts in the lecture (control) group. Pujiastuti, and Haryadi, (2023) study revealed that Guided-inquiry Learning can further enhance students' mathematical literacy skills than the Direct Instruction Learning, however, this study did not consider interest of students towards mathematics. Sunday, Olaoye, and Audu (2021) study reveal that there is significant difference between the achievement of students exposed to cooperative strategy and those exposed to conventional method. This shows that cooperative learning methods improve students' achievement in mathematics and attitude towards mathematics. Lekan and Emmanuel (2020) study revealed that students in the cooperative learning strategy group retention ability in Mathematics was higher than compared to those in the conventional group. Anigbo (2016), Aligba and Abaver (2022) study revealed that the experimental group had improved their interest towards set theory after a student-centered strategy was used.

Gender is a socio-cultural concept that differentiates the roles of boys and girls in a given society. These are the physical, biological, mental and behavioral characteristics that distinguish between the masculine and the feminine (male and female) population. Gender could relate with student' interest in the learning process. Gender issue in Mathematics has posed a lot of worry and has attracted many researchers, studies on gender as it affects student' interest in Mathematics are inconclusive, hence the need for more investigations. The mathematics field has been for years considered as a male business, this could be the reason why the female students' show little effort towards learning and excelling in it, hence only few females are professionals in Mathematics. Gender differences in Mathematics achievement and ability has remained a source of concern as researchers seek to address the under-representation of women at the highest levels of Mathematics, physical sciences and engineering. According to Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) on the influence on gender differences in Mathematics interest and achievement of junior secondary school students in Niger State, the findings revealed that male students excelled in Mathematics more than their female counterparts furthermore, Allahnana, Akande, Vintseh, Alaku and Alaku (2018) researched on assessment of Gender and interest in Mathematics achievement in Keffi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study findings revealed that male students have interest in Mathematics concepts more than their female counterparts. None of the studies reviewed considered guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative strategies as instructional strategies that could enhance students' interest in Mathematics concepts such as geometry.

Interest in learning concept geometry could be stimulated by the strategies used in learning Mathematics concepts, this could in turn enhance student's active participation and enable better achievement scores. The persistent poor performance of students in Mathematics external examinations such as the Basic Education Certification Examinations (BECE) is of great concern in Nigeria and in Benue State (Ocheche & Oguche, 2022) This is not in exemption to special education school students with special needs, who also study Mathematics using the same Mathematics curriculum and also partake in the external examinations (Ballin, Davidson, Caron, & Drago, 2022). The Chief examiner's reports of Basic Education Certificate Examinations (BECE) from 2017-2022 portrays a concern, which shows that there is high level of impossibility of students passing BECE with 100 percent in Mathematics.

Table 1. Basic Education Certificate Examination 2017/2018-2021/2022 Result Review

Year	2017/2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022
Candidates	66,375	75,057	75,938	82,589	66,500
Average Score	56.91	56.03	51.59	63.67	66.63
Passed	61,705 (92.96%)	71,313 (95.01%)	65,422 (86.15%)	74,602 (90.33%)	60600 (91.13%)
Failed	4,670 (7.04%)	3,744 (4.99%)	10,516 (13.85%)	7,987 (9.67%)	5,900 (8.87%)

Lack of interest and motivation in Mathematics concepts such as Geometry could be traced to Conventional learning strategies such as lecture methods used by teachers to teach. Innovative learning strategies such guided-inquiry strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies could be avoided by teachers with the intention to maximize time, since student's interaction could be more time consuming compared to lecture method. Thus, they persistently use Conventional learning strategy to teach the students. This has aggravated matters as students become passive rather than active learners. Conventional learning strategy are teacher-centered and do not provide opportunity for collaborative learning. Low rate of

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stimulation of students in learning Mathematics concepts could have great effect on students with special needs interest and could furthermore, create Mathematics phobia and a feeling of inability in solving mathematical problems.

The literature review accessed by the researcher has shown that research has being scarcely carried out on education of students with special needs in Benue State in Mathematics. There are few studies in Benue State on guided-inquiry strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies, however, they are not on students with special needs. Due to insufficient research on students with special needs education in Mathematics concepts such as Geometry, this study seeks to investigate the "Effects of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State"

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry among secondary school students in Benue State. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the effect of Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry of students with special needs in Benue State
2. Examine the effect of Guided-Inquiry strategy on Interest in Concept Geometry of male and female students with special needs in Benue State
3. Investigate the effect of Coop-Coop Cooperative strategies on Interest in Concept Geometry of male and female students with special needs in Benue State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?
2. What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy?
3. What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level.

1. There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.
2. There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy.
3. There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Methodology

The study adopted Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, posttest non-equivalent research design. This design was considered appropriate for this study because intact classes were used and no possibility of randomization of the research participants. Emaikwu (2015) opined that the design is deemed suitable because the participants of the research were not randomized as in true experiment. Population of the study comprise of all government junior secondary school class three (JSSIII), 2022/2023 academic session students with special needs in Benue state. A sample size of 46 (28 Male and 18 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. Two special secondary schools were used as experimental groups, which were taught concept Geometry using Guided-inquiry and Coop-Coop cooperative instructional strategies respectively. Intact classes where used, this was to ensure that the classes were not randomized and disarranged. The criteria was that the schools must be special schools, also, one school should be used for each of the two groups. The justification for simple random sampling was to ensure that all the six special needs secondary schools had the same opportunity to be picked, in order to eliminate selection bias. This helps to remove the disparity of schools in terms of validity of the study.

One instrument was developed by the researchers for data collection. Interest in Geometry Scale (IGS). Ten lesson plans were prepared for teaching. Five (5) lesson plans for teaching in each experimental group; guided-inquiry instructional strategy experimental group and coop -coop co-operative instructional strategy experimental group respectively. IGS is a 20-

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item researcher-developed rating scale with three sections developed by the researcher, each designed to measure the respondents' interest in Geometry. Section A sought the respondents' demographic data, section B contained ten (10) items designed to determine the students' interest in Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategies and section C also had ten (10) items designed to determine the students' interest in Geometry using coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies. The items of the instrument (IGS) include interchanged positive and negative statements for guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies. The statements were rated Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD); with scoring of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, with reverse scoring pattern for negative statements.

The IGS and lesson plans were validated by two experts in Mathematics Education and one in measurement and evaluation Benue State University, Makurdi. The comments and suggestions were used to improve the quality of the instrument and lesson plans. Pilot testing was conducted in another special school not among the two selected for the study, and an intact class was used of upper basic three students with special needs. The IGS reliability index of 0.76 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. A pretest was administered to both experimental groups to determine students' homogeneity before the treatment. After the pretest, the research assistants taught experimental group 1 using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and experimental group 2 were taught using coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy. After treatment, the research assistants administered the post-IGS to determine students' interest in learning Geometry when taught using guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies. Teachers that participated in the study were Mathematics teachers teaching in those classes as their regular teachers, who have a minimum of three years' experience and graduates of Mathematics Education from either teaching colleges or other higher institutions of education.

In all the schools, the treatment procedural lasted for five weeks. Training of research assistants was held in the first week, while the pre-test conducted in the second week. Treatment of experimental group 1 and experimental group 2 were carried out simultaneously in the third, to fifth week. Post-test was administered in the fifth week. Before the commencement of the training, the researcher explained the objectives of the study to the research assistants and revealed the teaching packages for guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategies for the two experimental groups to the research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Interest Ratings of Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry and Coop-Coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy.

Instructional Strategy	N	Pre-IGS		Post-IGS		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Guided Inquiry	29	2.6	0.04	3.01	0.35	0.39
Coop-Coop Cooperative	17	2.51	0.42	3.09	0.30	0.58
Mean Difference		0.11		0.08		0.03

Table 2 shows that students taught using guided inquiry had mean Pre-IGS and Post-IGS of 2.62 and 3.01 with standard deviation of 0.40 and 0.35 respectively. Students taught using coop-coop co-operative group had mean Pre-IGS and Post-IGS of 2.51 and 3.09 with standard deviation of 0.42 and 0.30 respectively. The mean difference in Pre-IGS and Post-IGS for students taught using guided-inquiry and coop-coop co-operative is 0.11 and 0.08. The mean difference between the mean Pre-IGS and Post-IGS of students taught using guided inquiry is 0.39 while that of students taught using coop-coop co-operative is 0.58 with mean gain difference of 0.03. This difference indicates that coop-coop co-operative strategy has more effect in enhancing students' interest than guided-inquiry strategy.

Research Question 2

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What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation between Interest Ratings of male and female Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry Instructional Strategy.

z	N	Pre-IGS		Post-IGS		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Student' Gender						
Male	17	2.62	0.37	3.00	0.23	0.38
Female	12	2.26	0.46	3.05	0.48	0.43
Mean Difference		0.00		0.05		0.05

Table 3 shows that the mal mean pre-IGS interest rating of male students in the guided-inquiry group is 2.62, with 0.37 standard deviation, while the mean pre-IGS interest rating of female is 2.26 with standard deviation of 0.46. The difference between the mean pre-IGS interest rating of male and female students is 0.00. The mean post-IGS interest rating of male students is 3.00, with standard deviation of 0.23. While the female has mean post-IGS interest rating of 3.05 with standard deviation of .48. The difference between the mean post-IGS interest rating of the male and female students is 0.05. The mean gain of male students is 0.38, while that of female students is 0.43, with 0.05 increase in favor of female students. This implies that female students obtained higher interest ratings when taught geometry using guided-inquiry strategy.

Research Question 3

What is the difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation between Interest Ratings of Male and Female Students' with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Coop-Coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy.

Student' Gender	N	Pre-IGS		Post-IGS		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Male	11	2.54	0.47	3.12	0.29	0.58
Female	6	2.45	0.37	3.04	0.34	0.59
Mean Difference		0.09		0.08		0.01

Table 4 shows that the mean pre-IGS interest rating of male students in the coop-coop co-operative strategy group is 2.54, with 0.47 standard deviation, while the mean pre-IGS interest rating of female is 2.45 with standard deviation of 0.37. The difference between the mean pre-IGS interest rating of male and female students is 0.09. The mean post-IGM interest rating of male students is 3.12, with standard deviation of 0.29. While the female has mean post-IGS interest rating of 3.04 with standard deviation of 0.34. The difference between the mean post-IGS interest rating of the male and female students is 0.08. The mean gain of male students is 0.58, while that of female students is 0.59, with 0.01 increase in favor of female students. This implies that female students obtained higher interest ratings when taught geometry using guided inquiry strategy.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Table 5: ANCOVA of Mean Interest Ratings of Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-inquiry and Coop-coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy.

Source	Type III Squares	Sum of Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
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Corrected Model	.281 ^a	2	.141	1.280	.289	.056
Intercept	13.234	1	13.234	120.521	.000	.737
Pre-IGS	.204	1	.204	1.854	.180	.041
Strategy	.048	1	.048	.434	.513	.010
Error	4.722	43	.110			
Total	429.549	46				
Corrected Total	5.003	45				

a. R Squared = .056 (Adjusted R Squared = .012)

Table 5 results summary reveals that $F(1, 43) = .434$; $p = 0.513 > 0.05$. This signifies that the probability level is greater than the specified alpha-level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is retained. This means that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy.

Table 6: ANCOVA of Mean Interest Ratings Between Male and Female Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry Instructional Strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	.195 ^a	2	.098	.772	.473	.056	
Intercept	7.933	1	7.933	62.657	.000	.707	
Pre-IGS	.163	1	.163	1.287	.267	.047	
Gender	.030	1	.030	.236	.631	.009	
Error	3.292	26	.127				
Total	265.628	29					
Corrected Total	3.487	28					

a. R Squared = .056 (Adjusted R Squared = -.017) s

Table 6 results summary reveals that $F(1, 26) = .236$; $p = 0.631 > 0.05$. This signifies that the probability level is higher than the specified alpha-level of .05. Hence the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Table 7: ANCOVA of Mean Interest Ratings between Male and Female Students with Special Needs Taught Concept Geometry Using Guided-Inquiry Instructional Strategy Using Coop-coop Co-operative Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	.074 ^a	2	.037	.379	.691	.051	
Intercept	5.199	1	5.199	53.355	.000	.792	
Pre-IGS	.053	1	.053	.547	.472	.038	
Gender	.028	1	.028	.290	.599	.020	
Error	1.364	14	.097				
Total	163.921	17					
Corrected Total	1.438	16					

a. R Squared = .051 (Adjusted R Squared = -.084)

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Table 7 results summary reveals that $F(1, 14) = .290$; $p = 0.599 > 0.05$. This signifies that the probability level is higher than the specified alpha-level of .05. Hence the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the current study reveals that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of students with special needs taught concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and those exposed to coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy. This finding contradicts Lekan and Emmanuel's (2020) findings which revealed that students in the cooperative learning strategy group retention ability in Mathematics was higher than compared to those in the conventional group. This finding also contradicts Sunday, Olaoye, and Audu's (2021) finding which reveal that there is significant difference between the achievement of students exposed to co-operative strategy and those exposed to conventional method. This shows that guided-inquiry instructional strategy and co-operative learning methods improve students' interest towards mathematics. This is possible since; the two instructional strategies are learner-centered and student activity-based learning strategies.

The finding is in cognizance with Ijeh's (2023) finding that there is significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught Mathematics with inquiry-based instructional strategy group and their counterparts in the lecture group, and Aligba and Abaver's (2022) finding that students in the experimental group had improved their interest towards set theory after a student-centered strategy was used, compared to conventional methods. These findings though contradicting, indicates that learner-centered strategies will have a greater influence on students' interest compared to conventional methods such as lecture methods. But when two learner-centered strategies; guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy are used, the effect will be the same. This signifies that their effect is the same on the students' interest since they share similarities of students' activity-based classes and the teachers' guidance of the student to discover knowledge and self-evaluate the achievement of the lesson's objectives.

The findings from the present study reveals that there is no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using guided-inquiry instructional strategy, neither between mean interest ratings of male and female students with special needs taught Concept Geometry using coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy. These findings are contrary to the finding of Allahnana, Akande, Vintseh, Alaku and Alaku (2018) which revealed that male students have interest in Mathematics more than their female counterparts. Furthermore, the study of Oluyemo, Musbahu, Kukwil, Anikweze and Shaluko (2020) findings revealed that male students excelled in Mathematics more than their female counterparts also contradicts the current study's findings. Mathematics has been considered as a hard subject that requires critical, analytical and creative thinking and as such is often regarded as a male subject, the findings of this study shows that with the use of student-centered strategies; guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop cooperative instructional strategy, both male and female students with special needs interest in mathematics concepts can be boosted.

Conclusion

Guided inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy could be suitable for teaching Geometry in secondary school students with special needs to enhance their interest. This is because, these strategies have positive effect of boosting interest in Geometry, using guided-inquiry and coop-coop cooperative instructional strategies on students with special needs in Benue State. Guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy are also, found to enhance students with special needs interest irrespective of gender.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study.

1. The use of guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy should be encouraged in special secondary schools for students with special needs. This will motivate students with special needs and also, boost their interest in learning mathematical concepts such as geometry.
2. Government and education stakeholders should encourage the teaching and learning of mathematics concepts using guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy, which will stimulate both male and female students with special needs interest in learning Mathematics concepts.

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3. Curriculum planners should inculcate learner-centered strategies such as guided-inquiry instructional strategy and coop-coop co-operative instructional strategy in Mathematics concepts curriculum in order to enable students with special needs interact and collaborate during learning.

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